

Development of Improved Charcoal-Fueled Cookstove for Cooking Applications in Rural Households

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Abstract. In the Philippines, charcoal is among the preferred fuel types used for residential cooking and water boiling applications. However, charcoal combustion emissions are known to contain compounds toxic to human health. It is estimated that millions of Filipinos residing in households that use charcoal for cooking and water boiling may be exposed to alarming concentrations of household air pollutants (HAP). Indoor exposure of residents is a function of many variables such as fuel combustion efficiency, fuel type, emission exhaust from the dwelling space, ventilation, and kitchen placement and orientation. The study focused on the development of an improved cookstove, the assessment of its performance, and the impact of its use on the exposure of a simulated occupant. A modified water boiling test was conducted, based on the protocol developed by the Global Alliance for Clean Cookstoves. Cookstove performance was quantified using the former's ready-made e-spreadsheet. HAP considered in the study were carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, and both respirable and inhalable particulate matter. Physical conditions (dry bulb temperature and relative humidity) were also assessed.

INTRODUCTION

According to the World Health Organization, around 3 billion people still rely on the use of biomass fuels such as wood, charcoal, dung, and crop wastes, in order to meet their energy requirements in terms of cooking and heating applications. In the Philippines, biomass fuels provide approximately 30 percent of the energy used which are mostly consumed for household cooking by the residents living in rural communities. However, biomass fuels are typically burned using simple and inefficient stoves which may lead to the emission of various pollutants such as carbon monoxide, particulate matter, and other harmful substances at relatively high concentrations. These pollutants can significantly affect the indoor air quality (IAQ), which can result in health issues in exposed individuals. By improving the design of typical biomass cookstoves, the emissions of harmful pollutants in such built environments may be significantly reduced.

A study was conducted by Chen et al. in 2014, which featured the development of three (3) improved cookstoves and comparison of the cookstove performance and simulated exposures. The study was presented by Belino et al. during the Asia-Pacific Conference on the Built Environment in 2015. The two studies mentioned served as the

foundation of this research, which included an increased number of trials for each cookstove tested. This study is the first part of a series of studies aimed at replicating the methodology used in the previous studies mentioned, but with more trials for each cookstove.

METHODOLOGY

Design and Fabrication of the Cookstove

The design of the improved cookstove was based on the Burn cookstove configuration and the study of Belino et al. Slight modifications were applied to the design of the previous study's prototype. Stainless steel was chosen as the primary material for the stove, considering its thermal properties and strength. The significant parts of the cookstove are the following: firebox (venue for fuel combustion), insulation, grate, ashtray, and covers. Perlite was used as insulation material between the firebox and the outer body. The fabrication of the cookstove was outsourced to a machine shop (New Hong Lee Tinsmith Corp). Computer modeling was not used during the design process. Table 1 shows the information about the major parts of the cookstove.

TABLE 1. List of significant parts and dimensions of the cookstove

Stove Parts	Material	Parameters	Values (mm)
Firebox	Stainless Steel	Diameter	140
		Height (from top to grate)	70
		Height (from grate to ashtray)	30
		Wall Thickness	1.5
Insulation	Perlite	Height	100
		Thickness	85
Grate	Stainless Steel	Diameter of grate surface	140
		Diameter of holes	8
Ashtray	Stainless Steel - polished	Length	140
		Width	190
		Height	40
		Thickness	1
Bottom / Side Cover	Stainless Steel	Diameter of bottom cover	225
		Height	140
		Thickness	1
Top Cover	Stainless Steel	Inner Diameter	145
		Outer Diameter	225
		Thickness	1

Water Boiling Test (WBT)

A modified WBT was used to measure the cookstove performance. The WBT was based on the procedure by the Global Alliance for Clean Cookstoves version 4.2.3. The WBT requires three test phases, namely the cold start, hot start, and simmer phases. The cold start phase is the first phase of the WBT wherein the cookstove and 2.5 L of water are initially at room temperature. The cold start phase is immediately followed by the hot start phase, where 2.5 L of water at room temperature is heated, using the same stove which is still hot. The simmer phase comes after the hot start phase, where the remaining water from the previous phase is constantly heated within 3 °C below the boiling point for 45 minutes. The cold and hot start phases end when the water has come to a consistent boil. Parameters measured at the start and at the end of each phase were the initial temperature of the water, the weight of the pot with and without water, the weight of both the charcoal and the resulting ash, and the clock time.

FIGURE1. Modified Burn Cookstove (a) Internal view of cookstove without insulation and upper cover, (b) Front View, (c) Top View

Experimental Set-Up

The Foundry Room inside the Mapua University campus was used as the venue for the experimentation. The existing overhead hood in the room was never activated in all trials and was covered to naturally induce ventilation through the door and window only. The Foundry Room dimensions are 3.75 m x 6 m x 3 m (L x W x H). The experimental set-up used in the study by Belino et al. was adopted. To simulate the exposure that an occupant operating the cookstove might experience, IAQ-related parameters were gathered at the breathing zone 1.58 m from the ground. The IAQ measurement equipment was placed on a platform and was situated 60 cm away from the cookstove. Another hygrometer was used to measure conditions at a distance from the cookstove. Figure 2 shows the experimental set-up used. A total of four (4) WBT were conducted.

Assessment and Evaluation of Contaminants

The summary of the equipment and protocols used in IAQ measurement is shown in table 2. Background measurements were taken for all parameters of interest prior to each WBT.

Table 3 shows the limits of concern from various organizations used to evaluate the indoor contaminants measured. CO₂ and PM limits of concern were compared to those from the American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH). CO concentration was evaluated based on the World Health Organization (WHO) limit of concern.

TABLE 2. IAQ Equipment and sampling protocols used

IAQ Parameter	Equipment used	Equipment Description	Protocol
Carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	Telaire 7001	Digital, direct reading, passive	Every 3 minutes, taken at the breathing zone and outdoor
Carbon monoxide (CO)	Honeywell	Colorimetric tubes with manual hand pump, passive	After cold and hot start phases, 15 and 45-minute mark of simmering phase, taken at the breathing zone
Particulate matter, inhalable (PM _i) and respirable (PM _r)	SKC IOM sampler (25 mm, 0.8 um MCE filter; MultiDust Foam Discs)	Size-selective, Gravimetric, battery operated pump	All phases, time of sampling depends on the time of phase or 30 minutes maximum, taken at the breathing zone and outdoor
Temperature and relative humidity	TFA	Digital, direct reading, passive	Every 3 minutes, taken at the breathing zone, foundry room, and outdoor

TABLE 3. Limits of concern used to evaluate the indoor air quality parameters

Parameters	Limit values	Exposure Duration	Agency
CO ₂	5000 ppm	8-h TWA	ACGIH
CO	90 ppm	15-min TWA	WHO
PM _i	10,000 µg/m ³	Ceiling	ACGIH
PM _r	3,000 µg/m ³	Ceiling	ACGIH

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Indoor Air Quality

Carbon dioxide

Table 4 shows the summary of CO₂ concentrations recorded. Data was collected from two sampling points namely the breathing zone and outdoor. The average CO₂ concentration was highest during the hot start phase but was only slightly higher (40 ppm) than the average CO₂ concentration during the cold start phase. The concentration was lowest during simmer phase. Outdoor CO₂ concentration remained nearly constant and was observed to be at the expected concentration range during all trials. The CO₂ TWA concentration was 623 ppm, which was significantly below the ACGIH limit.

FIGURE 2. Experimental set-up of the WBT and IAQ assessment (dimensions in cm): (a) Front view with equipment labeled and (b) isometric view of the laboratory set-up used

Carbon monoxide

The summary of CO concentrations observed is shown in Table 5. CO concentration was observed to be highest during the cold start phase in most trials and usually decreased during succeeding WBT phases. The average CO concentrations reflected this observed trend. The lowest CO concentrations occurred at the end of the simmer phase. The average CO concentrations did not exceed the limit of concern. However, there were two instances during the WBT (once each during hot and cold start) wherein the CO concentration exceeded the limit by as much as 38 ppm.

TABLE 4. Summary of CO₂ concentrations during each WBT phase.

WBT Phase	n	Mean (ppm)	Range (ppm)	S.D. (ppm)
Background	4	665	323	134
Cold Start	4	1,330	211	89
Hot Start	4	1,370	528	225
Simmer	4	993	620	265
Outdoor	4	522	119	56

TABLE 5. Summary of CO concentrations at the breathing zone during each WBT phase.

WBT Phase	N	Mean (ppm)	Range (ppm)	S.D. (ppm)
Background	4	0	0	0
Cold Start	3	81	28	16
Hot Start	4	71	98	41
Simmering (15 min)	4	25	34	15
Simmering (45 min)	4	10	19	11

TABLE 6. Summary of PM_i concentrations during each WBT phase.

WBT Phase	N	Mean (µg/m ³)	Range (µg/m ³)	S.D. (µg/m ³)
Background	4	2,500	3,333	1,667
Cold Start	2	6,211	8,091	5,721
Hot Start	4	5,892	7,137	2,941
Simmer	3	926	1,111	641
Outdoor	2	1,389	556	393

TABLE 7. Summary of PM_r concentrations during each WBT phase.

WBT Phase	N	Mean (µg/m ³)	Range (µg/m ³)	S.D. (µg/m ³)
Background	4	1,389	1,666	1,178
Cold Start	4	2,456	2,012	863
Hot Start	4	4,193	6,796	2,958
Simmer	4	695	555	278
Outdoor	3	556	0	0

Stove Performance

Table 8 shows the summary of the performance data of the improved cookstove. Comparing the improved cookstove to the International Workshop Agreement (IWA) 11:2012 Guidelines for Evaluating Cookstove Performance, the improved cookstove attained tier 1 for thermal efficiency and tier 3 for specific fuel consumption. Table 9 shows the tiers for efficiency and fuel use.

Stove performance and IAQ

The HAP that were observed to peak during the cold start phase were CO₂, CO, and PM_i, while CO₂ and PM_r peaked during the hot start phase only. The presence of high HAP concentrations appeared to coincide with cookstove operation (WBT phase) with high specific fuel consumption, high firepower, and low thermal efficiency.

TABLE 8. *Summary of performance of the improved cookstove*

Parameters	N	Mean	Maximum	Minimum	S.D.
Time to boil (minutes)	4	13.16	15.40	11.90	1.32
Specific fuel consumption (g of fuel/L boiled)	4	47.83	55.50	28.90	10.69
Firepower (W)	4	3,693.50	5,593.00	700.00	2,143.51
Thermal efficiency (%)	4	26.92	39.00	21.00	6.84

TABLE 9. *IWA 11:2012 tiers for efficiency and fuel use.*

Tier	High Power Thermal Efficiency (%)	Low Power Specific Consumption (MJ/min/L)
Tier 0	< 15	> 0.050
Tier 1	≥ 15	≤ 0.050
Tier 2	≥ 25	≤ 0.039
Tier 3	≥ 35	≤ 0.028
Tier 4	≥ 45	≤ 0.017

CONCLUSION

The study was able to develop an improved cookstove that performed significantly better than the 'typical' cookstove that was used in a past study by Belino et al. The 'typical' cookstove used as the benchmark for the improved cookstove performance obtained a thermal efficiency of 11% while the improved cookstove featured in this study achieved an average of 26.92% thermal efficiency.

The assessment of selected HAP within the vicinity of a solid fuel-fired cookstove suggested that occupants of households which use charcoal as fuel for cooking may potentially be at risk of exposure to dangerous concentrations of CO and PM_r, since these HAP were observed to exceed the limit of concern. This is considering that the cookstove used in this study is already an "improved" cookstove, which was expected to perform substantially better in terms of HAP emission and cookstove performance than more affordable cookstoves that are typically sold in wet markets in the Philippines or improvised cookstoves constructed by residents themselves out of easily obtainable materials i.e. concrete.

The increased number of trials performed has increased the amount of reliable data as compared to the past studies that were used as bases for this study. The improvement of the data collected will complement the series of related studies that are planned to be conducted in the future by the authors.

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